

RECYCLING OF GLASS-FIBER-REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

The political and legal climate in Germany relating to the environment has been changing extremely rapidly. Great pressure has been placed upon the plastics industry to become responsible for the reuse and cost of their products at their end-of-life. Pressure has increased on the producing companies to not only design products which use recycled plastics, but also to design products which are more easily recycled, including dismantling, collection and sorting.

As a result of this pressure, the major companies from the SMC/BMC market designed and built a production-scale facility in 1991 to reprocess SMC/BMC scrap and used parts. This paper discusses the background, organization, and can be reprocessed and the resulting material used in new SMC parts of comparable quality and performance.

This public attitude and legal changes have already dramatically affected the outlook and the market for all plastic products. Landfill cost for plastic waste has risen in Europe to 100 ECU/ton making it more economical to recycle. In some States, landfills have been completely closed for industrial waste, restricting plastics, does not appear to be a viable solution since the public and local authorities are not accepting new facilities in their vicinity. Moreover, as safety concerns rise, the cost of the most advanced incineration plants which meet stringent standards have risen to 500 ECU/ton of waste material. Recycling has become not only a matter of economics but of survival (Figure 1).

While public awareness of environmental issues began to increase in the mid 80's, public and political pressure to implement rather than just plan has accelerated in the 90's. Surprisingly, other political issues like the opening of the East European market has not dampened the zest for environmental action.

SMC/BMC ARE RECYCLED ON A PRODUCTION SCALE

Thermosets were, until recently, considered to be non-recyclable. The SMC industry was forced to come up with a solution or surrender market share to other materials. Pressure from the automotive and electrotechnical industry - the main customers for SMC - was mounting to develop and prove the recyclability in order for SMC to be considered for any new applications.

A number of leading SMC producers and processors, namely BWR, Duroform, Menzolit and Mitras decided to act and founded ERCOM Composite Recycling GmbH in December 1990. Cofounders were the resin supplier BASF, Cray Valley and DSM, and glass fiber producers Owens Corning and Vetrotex.

As previously mentioned the newly proposed German Refuse act for Car Recycling with its priority for material recycling demonstrates that the ERCOM system is on the right track and offers a significant contribution to solve environmental issues.

ERCOM COMPLETES THE RESOURCE CYCLE

ERCOM offers a complete system to chose the loop between used parts from automotive service and disassembly plants and the reuse of fibrous reinforcing material in new SMC compounds (Figure 2).

- a MOBILE SHREDDING TRUCK crushes used parts at disassembly and production sites to reduce transportation cost
- transport the compacted material to a centralized fractionizing plant in Rastatt
- produce a range of fiber rich recycle material to sell back to SMC producers and others end users

SMC parts are generally large and bulky which makes them prime candidates for easy dismantling.

The mobile shredder and fractionizing plant have been in operation since the beginning of 1992.

MOBILE SHREDDER

The Mobile Shredder reduces the size of large parts to a chip size of about 2 x 2 inch filling a 30 m³ container with about 10 tons. This is a volume reduction of a factor of five. Compared to the transport of the large unshredded parts, this reduces transportation cost significantly. The commonly used metallic inserts in automotive parts do not have to be removed beforehand. In fact, preshredding to this predetermined chip size is an essential requirement to assure removal of metallic parts in the next processing step. Capacity of the shredder is approximately 3 tons/hr (Figure 3).

FRACTIONIZING PLANT AND PRODUCTION RANGE

The containers with preshredded material are docked at the fractionizing plant and then processed automatically through a series of pneumatic and mechanical fractionizing steps. It is essential to remove metallic and non metallic inserts from the preshredded material in a series of separation steps to assure a metal free product. A drying operation is included to assure the required low moisture level. A hammer mill is used for the grinding step.

The resulting fiber rich recycle can be produced in a series of fractions containing a mixture of glass fibers, fillers and resin. For example RC 1000 contains 40% glass fibers with a fiber length distribution up to 0,25 mm, whereas RC 3100 contains fibers between 6 mm to 20 mm (Table 1). The product is filled into BIG BAGS containing 500 kg up to 1 ton and shipped to customers. The operation is carried out in a completely closed system, clean and dust free. Operating approval of the system has been given by the German TÜV authority. Production throughput is up to 1,5 ton/hr, resulting in an output of 6000 tons/yr for a three shift operation. Operation is now carried out on a one shift basis, primarily with production scrap until volume builds up from repair service and disassembly operations.

It has been shown that this recovered new raw material from scrap and used parts offers a number of advantages in new SMC formulations. While strength and modulus can be maintained, there is an improvement in impact and, most significantly, a reduction in density resulting in a lower weight for a given car part (Table 2). The first commercial products contain 10 to 15% by weight of fiber rich recycle, parts with up to 50% are in the test phase. Approval for production has already been given for a number of automotive parts, for example noise barrier shields, spare wheel well and a class A painted front panel (Table 3).

Other end uses in the development phase are Compounding with other Resins, Polyurethane and Thermoplastic materials.

QUALITY

From the beginning of ERCOM the primary target for development was concentrated on the use of recyclate for primary parts - no DOWNCYCLING for materials since the market for garden posts, park benches and construction applications is already crowded with used plastic material from packaging.

This requires a system for Quality, starting with the collection of used parts to the delivery of recyclate to the customer. A system has been implemented to certify the condition of the material by the waste producer to assure a controllable input for the shredder operation. In addition, the properties of the recyclate like iron content, viscosity, particle size distribution and moisture are kept within prescribed limits.

EFFECTIVE POOLING OF RESOURCES

Management is directed by a supervisory board with representatives from its partners. It is open for participation of new members. The EUREKA* status has been awarded to ERCOM for this spear-head operation to enhance practical solutions to our environmental problems.

Project groups (staffed by individuals from the participating partners) for Logistics, Quality, Fractionizing Plant and New Product Development provide the necessary technical input to the operation. Marketing and Finance Committees support management.

Cooperative Agreement have been made with other organizations to develop FRP recycling in the USA, France and Japan.

CONCLUSIONS

The fact that thermoset material does not melt has shown an advantage in recycling, as the whole family of materials with the same resin base are compatible in recycling, independent of the formulation or the producer. This assures the necessary volume for logistics and processing required for satisfactory economics.

Twelve months after start up of the production plant, it is evident that all members of the recycling loop - from dismantler of used parts to user of recyclate - have to work together closely to assure a high quality product satisfactory for prime applications. The willingness to use recycled products has definitely increased. As production and sales volume build up, the economics of recycling become more and more favourable. SMC parts with recyclate can be offered at the same price as with virgin materials (Figure 4a + 4b). The ERCOM system can be used for other FRP materials, like Fenolics and Epoxy resins where similarity in technology and market structure exists.

RECYCLING: A REALITY FOR THE THERMOSET INDUSTRY

Although recycling of Thermosets and Composites started as a defensive action, it has become an opportunity giving an extra impulse to the branch. The future of Composites is so clear that they can impossibly be avoided. Re-use/recycling of Thermosets has now reached a stage that is comparable to that of Thermoplastics (Figure 5).

For the next five or seven years, the Thermoset industry has to draw up plans for a network of several milling plants in Europe. Valcor in France, an organization similar to ERCOM, could be the next activity in Europe (Figure 6). We must take into account that by the year 2000 some 100.000 tons of industrial and post-consuming waste will come back from the market each year and that this will have to be recycled.

It is surprising what we can do together.

* EUREKA is a European consortium to improve the competitive position of Europe compared to other regions. The projects for improved technology require partners from different European countries.

TABLE 1

Fiber length distribution for fractions

FIBERS with POWDER		FIBERS	
RC 1000	< 0,25 mm	RC 1100	0,5 - 3 mm
RC 2000	0,25 - 3 mm	RC 2100	3 - 6 mm
RC 3000	3 - 15 mm	RC 3100	6 - 20 mm

TABLE 2

Comparison of Properties Using Recyclate

	<u>Base</u>	<u>5%</u>	<u>10%</u>	<u>15%</u>
Flex-Strength (MPA)	194	222	185	208
Impact (KJ/m ²)	102	107	126	145
Density (g/cm ³)	1.90	1.85	1.80	1.72

Note: Recyclate content calculated as a percent of total weight of compound.

TABLE 3

Parts being developed with Recyclate

AUTOMOTIVE

- Audi 100
 - o Spare Wheel Well*
- BMW 3 series
 - o Sunroof Frame
- VW Passat
 - o Frontend (painted)*
- Polo
 - o Noise Barrier Shield*

TRUCK

- Mercedes Truck (over 6 tons)
 - o Bumper*
 - o Mounting Step*
 - o Front End Panel
 - o Noise Barrier Shield
 - o Air intake cover

* These parts are already in production or approved for production.

Waste cost Europe

Cost in Ecu's/ton

Material circulation Ercom GmbH

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

MOBILE SHREDDER

Density of SMC with increasing amount of recycle depending glass content

Influence of the amount of recylate on density and price (RMC) (% tot. glass by vol. constant)

ERCOM COMPOSITE RECYCLING

Situation within
5-7 Years

EUROPE/WORLD